

MANAGEMENT OF SCHOOL COMMUNITY RELATIONSHIP PROGRAM IN INCREASING COMMUNITY PARTICIPATION AT SMAN 1 AMPANA KOTA, TOJO UNA- UNA REGENCY

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Abstract

The Management of School–Community Relations Program to Enhance Community Participation (At SMAN 1 Ampana Kota). This research aims to describe: (1) the planning of the school–community relations program; (2) the implementation of the school– community relations program; (3) the impact of the school–community relations program; and (4) the supporting and inhibiting factors of the school–community relations program. This study uses a qualitative approach. Data collection techniques include interviews, documentation studies, and observations. The data analysis process involves data collection, data condensation, data presentation, and conclusion drawing. The results of the study show that: (1) The planning of the school–community relations program at SMAN 1 Ampana Kota is carried out through several stages, including planning, socialization, activity implementation, and evaluation. The school applies a collaborative approach with the community to achieve the program’s objectives; (2) The implementation of the school–community relations program involves the active roles of teachers and school staff in organizing activities and building effective communication with the community to foster active participation and support the sustainability of the program; (3) The impact of the school–community relations program on community participation includes increased community involvement in various school activities, such as parent meetings, social events, and school facility improvements. Moreover, this program has also shifted community perceptions about education. The community is increasingly aware of the importance of their contributions in supporting their children's education, which is reflected in their growing participation in school-organized activities; (4) The supporting and inhibiting factors of the school–community relations program include supporting factors such as awareness of the program's benefits, open communication between the school and the community, and the success of previous activities. Inhibiting factors include the community's limited time, lack of understanding of the program’s objectives, and geographical distance, which makes it difficult for some community members to attend school events. To overcome these obstacles, the school has taken measures to adjust activity schedules, improve socialization about the program's objectives, and provide better access for community members.

Keywords: management of school–community relations program, community participation.

Introduction

Education is the fundamental pillar in building the civilization of a nation. Through education, individuals are prepared to face life's challenges, become productive members of society, and develop their potential to the fullest. Education is not solely the responsibility of formal institutions such as schools, but also a shared responsibility among families, communities, and the government. These three elements are interrelated pillars in creating a quality and sustainable education system.

In practical terms, the implementation of formal education in schools cannot stand alone without the support of various parties. The community, particularly parents and those living around the school, plays a vital role in supporting the educational process. As stated explicitly in the Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 20 of 2003 on the National Education System, society has the right, duty, and responsibility in the administration of education. This confirms that community participation is a fundamental aspect of achieving national education goals.

However, the reality on the ground shows that the level of community participation in school education remains relatively low. Many members of the community tend to leave educational matters entirely to the schools and government, as if the responsibility lies solely with those institutions. The lack of collective awareness that educational success is a shared duty has resulted in minimal community involvement in school activities. Often, participation is limited to administrative matters, such as paying school fees, with little involvement in more substantive areas like planning, evaluation, or educational program development.

This phenomenon presents a serious challenge for education, especially for schools as the main providers of formal education. Schools must take strategic steps to build constructive relationships with the community. One concrete effort is the implementation of the School–Community Relations Program (commonly abbreviated as Husemas). This program aims to bridge communication between the school and the community to build synergy and mutually beneficial cooperation. Through Husemas, schools can communicate their vision, mission, programs, and needs to the public, while also providing space for community participation in the educational process.

At SMAN 1 Ampana Kota, the management of the Husemas program is highly relevant considering that the school operates under the Provincial Education Office of Central Sulawesi, which demands high standards of educational service. SMAN 1 Ampana Kota requires community support, both physical and non-physical, to provide quality education. Physical support includes financial assistance, manpower, infrastructure, and involvement in school activities. Non-physical support includes ideas, oversight, constructive feedback, and strategic partnerships with external institutions related to education. However, in practice, there are still obstacles such as limited parental involvement in school activities, delays in committee fee

payments, and a lack of community initiative in contributing to school development. These barriers indicate that communication and cooperation between the school and the community have not yet been optimized. In fact, the success of school education greatly depends on the synergy formed with the community as part of the educational ecosystem.

Through well-directed and systematic management of the Husemas program, schools can build trust and raise awareness among the community about the importance of their involvement in education. Husema's program is not merely ceremonial, but a managerial strategy to empower the community. In this context, community participation is not measured solely by the amount of money donated, but also by active involvement in decision-making, monitoring the educational process, and contributing to the creation of a conducive learning environment.

Optimal community participation also reflects good school governance. Schools that foster harmonious relationships with the community tend to gain greater support in improving education quality. Moreover, community involvement can serve as a channel for schools to receive input, criticism, and innovations that drive continuous improvement.

According to Arikunto, the importance of Husemas in education lies in: (1) its role as a necessary activity in all organizational work, providing schools or educational institutions with an official platform to connect with the wider community and showcase what has been, is being, and will be done; (2) its function as a medium through which an organization can disseminate ideas to other institutions or bodies; (3) its ability to facilitate assistance from external organizations or institutions; and (4) its encouragement of efforts by individuals or educational organizations to connect and build relationships with others.

Therefore, the school-community relationship must be able to function in developing institutional programs by applying how the relationship between the school and its public should be implemented. Leaders must be able to manage the activity process by mastering the theory of School-Community Program Management (Husemas) and its functions, namely: POAC (Planning, Organizing, Actuating, and Controlling) as proposed by George R. Terry (Suryosubroto, 2012).

The function of the School-Community Program Management aims to create and develop the best perception of an institution, organization, or educational institution, both directly and indirectly impacting the institution's future. Thus, schools must be a beacon for society. As a beacon, schools must serve as a role model in living a proper life for the community, empowering them in the process. At the same time, schools must also accommodate community aspirations and conditions by creating educational programs suited to society's needs.

With the existence of school-community relationships in education, cooperation among all parties will be established, both within the school (internal

public) and the general public (external public). This harmonious relationship will foster: (1) mutual understanding between schools, parents, the community, and other institutions within the community, including the world of work; (2) mutual support between schools and the community due to the realization of each party's importance and role; (3) strong cooperation between schools and various stakeholders, making them proud and jointly responsible for the school's success; (4) increased community participation, support, and concrete contributions; (5) the emergence and strengthening of greater community responsibility for the effective and efficient continuation of school education programs; (6) community involvement in solving problems faced by the school; (7) establishment and development of a favorable image of the school.

The Law of the Republic of Indonesia No. 20 of 2003, Article 54 states that community participation in education includes the involvement of individuals, groups, families, professional organizations, businesses, and community organizations in the implementation, supervision, and service of education.

Increasing community participation is not an easy task, as it requires integrated and comprehensive planning. This is related to the function of education as a gathering space for communities to maintain, learn, and enhance their social and cultural life. The same applies to SMAN 1 Ampana Kota, Tojo Una-Una Regency, where both in-school and out-of-school activities always apply the Husemas function so that activities can run well, with both internal and external communities indirectly participating.

Husema's activities implemented in the school aim to maintain good relations with all layers of society and increase active roles with the community. As practiced by SMAN 1 Ampana Kota, the presence of Husemas benefits both the educational institution and the community. Such activities encourage positive and active participation from the people of Tojo Una-Una Regency, especially in Ampana Kota District.

One of the high schools studied in Tojo Una-Una Regency is SMAN 1 Ampana Kota. Despite having some shortcomings, this school has many advantages, making it highly desired by the community and parents. For a long ago, SMAN 1 Ampana Kota has been the senior high school with the highest number of students in the regency. Many students register even before graduating from junior high school for fear of not being accepted due to limited capacity. Students who are not accepted at SMAN 1 then spread out and register at other high schools in the regency.

The advantages of this school include: (1) dissemination of information to parents and the general public is done via WhatsApp groups, website, Facebook, and other platforms, making it easier for parents and the community to access information about the school's developments; (2) the student admission process uses an online registration system, facilitating people across the regency—whether

from island areas, mountainous regions, or remote villages—to enroll their children without having to come to the school in person. This system has not yet been adopted by other schools in the regency; (3) SMAN 1 students have many achievements in competitions at sub-district, regency, provincial, and national levels; (4) the school regularly sends students to the provincial level to compete in Mathematics, Science Olympiads, as well as sports and arts; (5) the school has complete facilities and infrastructure; (6) it owns laboratories for computers, science, mathematics, and the arts; (7) it has sports fields for volleyball, badminton, futsal, and basketball; (8) it has a team of professional teachers, most of whom are civil servants, certified, with qualifications in undergraduate and postgraduate degrees, and work according to their field of expertise; (9) the school actively participates in the Indonesian Independence Day (HUT RI) and Tojo Una-Una Regency Anniversary (HUT Kabupaten); (10) it produces the best graduates in the regency, with many of its alumni receiving government scholarships for higher education; (11) the school has a high level of discipline, training students to be disciplined; (12) it has many collaborations with the government and external parties, such as with the Provincial and Regency Education Offices, the Police, BNN (National Narcotics Board), the Health Office, the Social Services, and BPJS. For example, they often invite the Police, BNN, and Health Office to conduct awareness sessions on health and drug abuse; (13) its location is in the heart of the city; (14) every year, SMAN 1 Ampana Kota organizes alumni reunions involving various activities such as fun walks, sports, art competitions, and more something not done by other schools in the regency.

Based on these unique characteristics, the researcher is interested in studying the management of the Husemas program in increasing community participation.

METHODS

This study employs a qualitative approach. The research takes a qualitative stance because the main focus of the research questions encompasses four key aspects: the planning of the HUSEMAS Program, its implementation, the supporting and inhibiting factors, and the impact of HUSEMAS on increasing community participation. These four focal points are difficult to analyze quantitatively, considering that this research aims to explore in depth the understanding and meaning behind the phenomena occurring. Therefore, careful and in-depth observation of the existing social environment is necessary, making the qualitative approach a more appropriate choice. This approach considers the research focus on four core elements of inquiry that consistently enrich the results: value, application, consistency, and neutrality (Lincoln & Guba, 1985: 290). Qualitative research presents detailed and in-depth findings, focusing on the

research location (natural environment). A qualitative approach allows for the discovery of descriptive data in the form of written, verbal, and behavioral expressions

that are empirically related to the research focus at SMAN 1 Ampana Kota.

The researcher believes that in-depth observation of the natural environment is essential to uncover the true content and meaning of the phenomenon being studied. This characteristic aligns with the principles of a qualitative approach, which aims to construct reality and understand the meaning behind it. The qualitative approach does not merely focus on the final outcome, but rather emphasizes the research process itself, with a focus on deep understanding of meanings and the expression of those meanings within relevant social contexts.

FINDING AND DISCUSSION

The following are the research findings that can be formulated based on the presentation of the case study at SMAN 1 Ampana Kota

1) Program Planning of School-Community Relations (HUSEMAS) at SMAN 1 Ampana Kota

The implementation of the School and Community Relations (HUSEMAS) program at SMAN 1 Ampana Kota demonstrates a structured and systematic approach, actively involving various stakeholders in all stages from planning to follow-up. The program begins with the issuance of a Decree (SK) by the school principal, which serves as the operational foundation for the Vice Principal of HUSEMAS in preparing a work plan aligned with the school's vision and mission. This is followed by cross-sectional coordination with operators, administrative staff, and the curriculum division to ensure data and program integration. The implementation of activities maximizes the involvement of principals, teachers, students, and the community through the use of various communication media, both modern (such as social media and radio broadcasts) and conventional (like letters and banners), to reach all layers of society. Strategies to increase community participation, especially from parents, are carried out through committee meetings, communication by homeroom teachers, and community-based activities such as mosque construction, involving community and religious leaders as well as school committees. The program is evaluated regularly to identify obstacles and develop approaches based on the needs of both the school and the community.

These findings align with Reeder's theory (in Listiyani et al., 2021), which emphasizes the importance of harmonious collaboration between schools and the public, and the theory of Soetopo & Soemanto (2013), which highlights the core principles of school-community relations: openness, participation, cooperation, and integration. The synergy between the school and the community not only increases public involvement in education but also creates a conducive, adaptive, and high-

quality educational ecosystem, resulting in students who are excellent, well-rounded, and competitive. Therefore, the success of the HUSEMAS program at SMAN 1 Ampana Kota proves that strategic partnerships between schools and communities are key to sustainable and quality education in the region.

2) **Implementation of the HUSEMAS Program at SMAN 1 Ampana Kota**

The implementation of the School and Community Relations (HUSEMAS) Program at SMAN 1 Ampana Kota has shown tangible success as a result of strong synergy among various stakeholders within the school environment, including the principal, teachers, operators, and the community. The school principal plays a central role through transformational leadership, as described by Bass (1990), which emphasizes the importance of vision, inspiration, and influence in driving positive change. The principal not only sets policies through a Decree (SK) on task distribution but also oversees program implementation and conducts regular evaluations to identify achievements, challenges, and areas for improvement.

Meanwhile, the Vice Principal in charge of HUSEMAS acts as a strategic liaison between the school and the community through a participatory communication approach. As Dale Carnegie suggests, strong relationships are built through active listening and persuasive communication. Communication is carried out through multiple channels, including WhatsApp, formal letters, and home visits to parents to foster transparency and mutual trust.

Teachers, especially homeroom teachers, play a significant role as emotional and educational connectors between the school and students' families, in line with Bronfenbrenner's ecological systems theory (1979), which stresses the importance of interaction between the microsystems (family and school) in child development. They actively communicate school activities, encourage parental involvement, and help students understand the values behind the programs.

School operators also play a critical role in managing accurate and timely information, serving as the basis for data-driven decision-making, as proposed by Schildkamp & Kuiper (2010). This cross-sectoral collaboration is evident in activities such as school committee meetings that involve religious leaders, parents, and government officials in planning the construction of a mosque, demonstrating the application of community-based education principles, which emphasize active community participation in education.

Overall, the success of the HUSEMAS Program at SMAN 1 Ampana Kota is not the result of a single party's efforts, but rather the outcome of effective leadership, strategic communication, strong collaboration, and a shared commitment to creating a school climate that supports academic, character, and spiritual development. This demonstrates that quality education can be achieved when schools open themselves to community participation, build a culture of collaboration, and develop systems responsive to local needs.

3) **Impact of the HUSEMAS Program on Community Participation**

The impact of the HUSEMAS program at SMAN 1 Ampana Kota can be seen in the significant increase in community involvement, especially among parents, in various school activities. This reflects the effective implementation of the HUSEMAS Program in strengthening communication and collaboration between the school and the community. The program has encouraged parents to actively contribute, whether in extracurricular activities, religious celebrations, or school facility development. For instance, the ongoing construction of a school mosque is entirely supported by the community and parents who contribute funds, materials, and labor. This participation not only improves school infrastructure but also strengthens the social bonds between the school and the wider community.

Moreover, the community's involvement is also evident in their quick response to administrative requests from the school. Parents show high awareness and concern for the school's administrative needs, such as providing or correcting student data for government records promptly. This demonstrates a shared responsibility in ensuring the success of their children's education. Additionally, during the student admission process (PPDB), the school noted a surge in applications beyond the available quota, with parents preparing the required documents well in advance. This indicates a high level of parental engagement in supporting their children's educational future.

In addition to parental involvement, alumni also contribute significantly by proposing and funding various student-centered activities, such as competitions and community walks. These initiatives aim to foster intergenerational connections and a sense of togetherness. Funding for these events often comes directly from alumni, further supporting school activities.

At the heart of all these successes is well-structured and effective communication. The HUSEMAS program ensures that school-related information is delivered clearly and on time to the school committee and parents. Likewise, the community's feedback is conveyed to the school via the committee, fostering a transparent and mutually supportive relationship. In this context, Epstein's theory of parental involvement (2001) highlights that parents' active participation in school activities contributes significantly to student success. Sanders (2001) further emphasizes the importance of community collaboration in creating a high-quality educational environment.

The researcher's observation on May 20 confirms these findings, with parents directly participating in the mosque construction project by donating materials and labor and working closely with the school based on joint agreements reached in committee meetings involving parents, community leaders, and school officials. Support from the government and local entrepreneurs also strengthens community solidarity in supporting education at SMAN 1 Ampana Kota.

Overall, this increased community involvement creates an inclusive educational atmosphere that supports improved education quality. Through the HUSEMAS program, strong communication between schools and the community has been established, benefiting not only academic activities but also extracurricular development and facility enhancement. Therefore, community involvement has had a significant positive impact, strengthening school-community relations and advancing the quality of education at SMAN 1 Ampara Kota.

4) **Supporting and Inhibiting Factors of the HUSEMAS Program in Increasing Community Participation at SMAN 1 Ampara Kota**

Based on an in-depth analysis of the driving factors behind community participation in the HUSEMAS Program at SMAN 1 Ampara Kota, it can be concluded that the increase in community involvement in various school activities is the result of a series of systematically and sustainably designed processes by the school. One of the main factors contributing to the success of this program is effective and transparent communication between the school and the community.

The school routinely conveys information related to programs and activities through various channels such as meetings, WhatsApp groups, letters, and face-to-face gatherings, which fosters strong trust between both parties. This clear communication generates a positive community response to each school initiative. In this context, the theory of effective communication by Shannon and Weaver (1949), which emphasizes the importance of clarity in delivering messages, is highly relevant, as well-received messages enhance participation and cooperation between the school and the community.

Additionally, active community involvement in various school activities, such as facility development, celebration of national holidays, and decision-making discussions, indicates that the community feels valued and shares responsibility for the school's progress. This aligns with Epstein's (2001) theory of parental involvement, which states that parents' active participation in their children's education positively contributes to educational quality. Parental participation in school activities—such as donating funds, building materials, and labor for facility projects—demonstrates their strong commitment to supporting educational continuity and the well-being of their children.

The local community's cultural characteristics, which place high value on education, further reinforce the success of this program. The community's sense of responsibility for the school in their neighborhood encourages them to play an active role in educational advancement. According to Banks' (2006) theory of educational culture, cultural values that support education can strengthen the relationship between school and community, ultimately increasing participation and educational quality. Transparency in program management and the publication of student achievements further enhance community trust in the educational quality

at SMAN 1 Ampana Kota. The school openly shares student developments and accomplishments, which motivates the community to contribute more to school activities. Furthermore, support from students' parents becomes another significant factor in increasing community participation. The ease of access to information provided by the school, accompanied by friendly service and personal engagement, makes parents feel appreciated and encouraged to contribute more actively.

The school's approach in listening to community needs and feedback strengthens the bond between both parties and creates mutually beneficial ties. This aligns with Public Relations Theory (Grunig & Hunt, 1984), which posits that open and responsive two-way communication can strengthen the relationship between institutions and their publics. The HUSEMAS Program at SMAN 1 Ampana Kota has successfully created synergy between the school and the community. This active participation is not merely spontaneous but the result of intensive communication, transparency, and consistent cultural engagement.

Through this program, the school and community have succeeded in establishing an inclusive and sustainable educational atmosphere. The HUSEMAS Program not only supports academic activities but also strengthens non-academic activities and school facility development. As explained in Sanders' (2001) theory of community collaboration in education, collaboration between schools and communities can create a supportive environment for higher-quality education. Thus, the success of the HUSEMAS Program at SMAN 1 Ampana Kota shows that with proper management, strong collaboration between school and community can provide sustainable and positive benefits for all involved parties, while also enhancing overall educational quality.

CONCLUSION

The conclusion of this discussion highlights that various theories and principles in educational management, school-community relations, and educational quality development play a crucial role in creating an effective and productive learning environment. Key concepts that stand out in improving education quality include transformational leadership, which emphasizes vision, clear communication, and empowering team members to achieve common goals. This type of leadership is particularly relevant in creating significant changes in the education system.

Moreover, harmonious relationships between schools, families, and communities are essential to foster synergy that supports children's holistic development. For example, Epstein's theory of family involvement teaches that collaboration between parents and schools can strengthen students' motivation and performance at school.

On the other hand, data-driven decision-making has become an increasingly important aspect of modern education. Data can be used to evaluate and adapt

educational programs to be more effective in meeting student needs and improving learning outcomes. Therefore, it is crucial for educators and policymakers to understand how to collect, analyze, and use data optimally in educational planning and evaluation. Furthermore, effective communication among all parties—educators, students, parents, and the community—is a key factor that must not be overlooked. The communication theory by Shannon and Weaver demonstrates that clear messages and good communication channels among stakeholders help prevent miscommunication, ultimately improving the performance and effectiveness of educational programs.

In general, to achieve optimal educational goals, active involvement from all elements is required, from planning to implementation and evaluation of the educational process. An approach that emphasizes collaboration, effective communication, and data-driven management is key to successfully addressing today's educational challenges. Therefore, the roles of school principals, teachers, parents, and the community in building a supportive educational ecosystem must be optimized. Consistently applying these principles at the school level, both inside and outside the classroom, will ensure a more qualified education that is relevant to future needs.

REFERENCES

- Arikunto, S. (2010). *Dasar-dasar evaluasi pendidikan*. Bumi Aksara.
- Bass, B. M. (1990). From transactional to transformational leadership: Learning to share the vision. *Organizational Dynamics*, 18(3), 19-31.
- Bronfenbrenner, U. (1979). *The ecology of human development: Experiments by nature and design*. Harvard University Press.
- Carnegie, D. (1936). *How to win friends and influence people*. Simon and Schuster.
- Epstein, J. L. (2001). *School, family, and community partnerships: Preparing educators and improving schools*. Westview Press.
- Grunig, J. E., & Hunt, T. (1984). *Managing public relations*. Holt, Rinehart and Winston.
- Harris, A. (2003). *School improvement: What's in it for schools?* Routledge.
- Lincoln, Y. S., & Guba, E. G. (1985). *Naturalistic inquiry*. SAGE Publications.
- Shannon, C. E., & Weaver, W. (1949). *The mathematical theory of communication*. University of Illinois Press.
- Schildkamp, K., & Kuiper, W. (2010). *Data-based decision making in education: Challenges and opportunities for teachers, school leaders, and policy makers*. Springer.
- Soetopo, P., & Soemanto, S. (2013). *Prinsip-prinsip hubungan sekolah dan masyarakat*. Jakarta: Grafindo.
- Suryosubroto, B. (2012). *Dasar-dasar manajemen pendidikan*. Rineka Cipta.
- Terry, G. R. (2012). *Principles of management*. Richard D. Irwin.
- Undang-Undang Republik Indonesia No. 20 Tahun 2003. *Sistem Pendidikan Nasional*. Pemerintah Republik Indonesia.